

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE LESSONS OF NATURAL GEOGRAPHY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *In this article important features of using innovative technologies in the lessons of natural geography of Uzbekistan were discussed. Through this article some interactive methods of teaching geography were noted.*

Key words: *innovative technologies, unique, conversational skills, social sciences, the graphic organizer "BBB", "Technology of working with red and green cards".*

In our republic new system of education has been formed – it is another step towards achieving world standards of education. Changes in education system lead to large-scale changes in teaching and development process of our children. Mastering innovative technologies by the teacher will help to correctly organize the educational process and develop intellectual, professional, moral, spiritual, civic and other qualities in students. If we want to be a competitive state, we must certainly develop our literacy in every sense of the word. The problem of education and development originates from the works of Ya. A. Kamensky. In his pedagogical research he says that it is necessary to pay attention to the natural distinctive features of the child and always remember the skills of the child. Of course, school time is unique and precious for the life of each student, because it is during this period that a cognitive interest in the environment is formed. Therefore, the school education is the main lever of continuing education for our children, which is a very complex and responsible work. School not only gives knowledge, but is essential part of general development, formation of oral speech, reading skills, correct perception of the environment, objective thinking, analysis skills, teaches to compare, prove, and develops conversational skills. The skills of primary school students are developed in two ways. First, is by receiving knowledge, skills, habits and practical development of them. Second, is by creative activities.

The educational activities differ from creative activities in that in creative activity, the students search for new methods of translating their ideas into reality. Based on the tasks set by the Law on Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, improving the quality and efficiency of education, the acquisition of modern knowledge, skills and abilities of pupils and students, the young generation with intellectual potential is a comprehensively developed person. Therefore, it is important to increase the outlook and knowledge and skills of students by improving the quality of education through the effective use of modern advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process. Radical reform of the education system in the country, raising it to the level of modern requirements, educating a harmoniously developed generation for the future has become a priority of state policy. The future of Uzbekistan depends primarily on the education of young people, their healthy upbringing, upbringing in the spirit of national idea, national ideology and devotion to their homeland, and the successful implementation of this complex process is one of the most pressing tasks of an independent country.

These days geography is considered as a part of the composite science of Human Society. Its purpose is to study the structure and behavior of human society. Therefore, it is one of the social sciences. Though all the social sciences have common purpose i.e. the study of man, yet each presents unique point of view and each has evolved its own technique of studying human affairs and solving social problems. Geography in the beginning did not have a very wide scope. It was limited in subject matter. Man, in fact, is a creature of nature which undergoes change constantly. It is the change which is the fundamental of the development & processes. Geography has also been a progressive & changing as well as dynamic subject. Now the scope of the subject of study of geography has widened and it has become very important. Every day we make use of the knowledge of this subject. Geography as a discipline can be split broadly into two main subsidiary fields: the human geography and the physical geography. The former largely focus on the built environment how humans create, view, manage, & influence space. The latter examines the natural environment, and how organisms, climate, soil, water and land focus produce & interact. The difference between these approaches led to a third field, the environmental geography which combines the physical and the human geography and looks at the interactions between the environment and humans. Geography today covers a vast field and comprises many branches of scholarship in its fold. Like the bee it sucks

honey from every flower. It subject matter consequently lends to end barrows interest from both scientist and student of social sciences, as it and includes physical sciences like physics, chemistry mathematics, and astronomy on the one hand and Natural and humanistic studies like any other science drives its raw material from other science sand it employs the derived raw material from its own angle and its own manner. Geography has its own unit of study the regions of the world .Each unit through interlinked has its own peculiarities. So, in each lesson teachers should utilize different methods in order to gather students' interest to the subject. Therefore, in the course of geography of Uzbekistan we will get acquainted with a two-hour practical lesson using the graphic organizer "BBB", "Technology of working with red and green cards".

➤ *(BBB) "graphic organizer.*

The first stage of the lesson is "I know. I found out. I want to know. (BBB) "graphic organizer. The group of students is divided into three subgroups, each group is named. (Names are chosen by the students themselves). The auditorium board is divided into three. At the top of the first section is written "I learned". The teacher then asks the students what they think about the new topic, and the concepts they describe are written in a column called "I know". This movement will continue until the students have finished their thoughts. It is necessary to ensure the activeness of all requirements in this process. Students cansay the same thing they think, even if it's wrong. After all, students are not limited in their activities. This approach builds in them the skills of free and independent thinking. The teacher asks the students what they understand about the new topic, knows the information, and encourages them to think again. The concepts and ideas expressed by the students are reflected in the column "I want to know". When the activity on both columns is completed, the teacher distributes the text on the topic to the students. The text is made up of basic information that students need to master. Once students have read the text, they should find the answer to the question of what else they have learned on the new topic. Each group of students describes the new concepts they have mastered after thinking about each other. The teacher writes the concepts mastered by them in the "I learned" column of the table on the board.

Strengthening knowledge using the technology of working with red and green cards.

The teacher distributes red and green cards to the students during the lesson. For each of the questions asked by the teacher, the students questions will be answered based on showing red (meaning Yes,

affirmative) or green (No-negative) colored cards. The teacher can ask the following questions:

- 1) Is the amount of oily hair unevenly distributed in Uzbekistan? (Yes)
- 2) Will the amount of precipitation in Uzbekistan increase from east to west? (No)
- 3) Will the surface structure of Uzbekistan rise from the north-west to the south-east? (Yes)

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